

Ion Exchange Selectivity of Monovalent Ions in Aqueous and 50% Ethanol-Water Media towards *Tris*-Trimethylene Diamine Co(III) Exchanged Amberlite-IRC-50

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The exchange isotherms of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from $\text{Na-Co}(\text{tn})_3$ -IRC-50 by monovalent ions in aqueous and 50% ethanol-water (v/v) media are of the S-type indicative of cooperative sorption. In aqueous solution the desorption efficiency of the ions is in the order: $\text{NH}_4^+ > \text{Li}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Rb}^+ > \text{Cs}^+$ while in 50% ethanol-water the sequence is $\text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Li}^+ > \text{Rb}^+ > \text{Cs}^+$. The extent of release of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from the resin matrix by each ion is much higher in 50% ethanol-water medium than in pure aqueous solution. It has been suggested that site binding of the ions with the resin followed by release of water molecules from the solvation shells of the participating species takes place. The plots of $\log(\text{selectivity coefficient})$ against both the hydrated ionic radius and the reciprocal of the Debye Hückel ion-size parameter a^* in aqueous medium are linear. This implies that both the parameters may be used to correlate the relative affinities of the monovalent ions for the resin surface.

STUDIES on ion exchange equilibria have revealed that the selectivity of a cation exchanger polymer is influenced by many factors such as the structure of the polymer, the nature of the functional group and the mole fraction of the exchanging cations in the polymer phase^{1,2}. Thus, the affinity sequence of the alkali metal cations in their exchange reactions in aqueous solutions on crosslinked polymethacrylic acid exchangers^{3,4} has been shown to be the reverse of that with polystyrene sulphonates^{5,6} where the order is: $\text{Cs}^+ > \text{Rb}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{Li}^+$. It has been suggested that in polymethacrylates specific association between the counter ions and the fixed ionic groups, i.e. site binding⁴, takes place and is accompanied by the release of water molecules from the solvation shells of the participating species. With polystyrene sulphonate exchangers, however, it has been inferred that ion-water interactions⁵ are of prime importance in determining the order of alkali metal cation selectivity. Recently Matsuura⁷ had proposed the use of cation exchange resins loaded with $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{3+}$ or $\text{Co}(\text{en})_3^{3+}$ for the continuous extraction of recoil products in Szilard-Chalmers reaction for obtaining a high yield and specific activity and found them most suitable for this method because these complex ions give rise to the bivalent cobaltous ion upon neutron irradiation^{8,9}. In view of the above theoretical and practical interests, the exchange characteristics of *tris*-trimethylene diamine Co(III) i.e. $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from $\text{Na-Co}(\text{tn})_3$ -IRC-50 against a number of monovalent ions in aqueous and 50% aqueous-ethanolic medium have been investigated and are reported here. The experimental exchange data have also been analysed in the light of the simple electrostatic model of Pauley¹⁰.

Materials and methods: Amberlite-IRC-50, a copolymer of methacrylic acid crosslinked with divinyl benzene and a carboxylic acid type exchanger (≈ 50 mesh particle sizes) was used. The exchange capacity of the H-resin was found to be 1020 meq/100 g of the dry resin (dried at 105°) and was determined by shaking the resin with a measured excess of standard NaOH solution and then back titrating the excess alkali with HCl. The H-exchanger was converted into the Na-form by adding an equivalent amount of NaOH. The experimental details for studying the exchange of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ onto Na-resin and its subsequent desorption by the monovalent ions are similar to those reported earlier¹¹. The hydration status of H^+ , Na^+ and $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ saturated resins were determined with the help of a modified apparatus as used by Bayer¹². The intake of water per g of resin gives an idea of the relative hydration characteristics of the solids.

Results and Discussion

The maximum uptake of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ onto Na-form of Amberlite IRC-50, a weak carboxylic cation exchanger, corresponds to 704 meq/100 g as against the exchange capacity of the resin which is 1020 meq/100 g. The lower value may be caused by the physical inaccessibility of some of the exchange sites of the resin to the large-sized $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ ions. It is interesting to note from Fig. 1 that the exchange isotherms of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from $\text{Na-Co}(\text{tn})_3$ -IRC-50 with the monovalent ions in aqueous and 50% aqueous ethanolic media are of the S-type in the classification of sorption isotherms of Giles *et al.*¹³. Moreover, the general lyotropic series is also reversed in aqueous medium except in

Fig. 1. Exchange isotherms of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_2^{2+}$ from $\text{Na-Co}(\text{tn})_2\text{-IRC-50}$ by monovalent ions in aqueous (O) and 50% aqueous-ethanolic medium (●).

the position of NH_4^+ . The S-type of isotherms indicate cooperative adsorption i.e. adsorption occurs with increasing ease as solute concentration increases in the initial part of the isotherm, suggesting that adsorbed molecules encourage the retention of additional like-molecules. Recent theoretical treatment by Giles¹⁸ *et al.*, however, shows that this type of curve occurs when the activation energy for desorption of the solute is concentration dependent, and/or is markedly reduced by large negative contributions of the solvent or a second solute.

The intake of water by H^+ , Na^+ and $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_2^{2+}$ forms of the resin are 2.1, 3.6 and 1.78 ml per g of the resins respectively. The data clearly show that a hydrophobic character is developed in the resin matrix when H^+ or Na^+ is replaced by $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_2^{2+}$, while a hydrophilic character is noticed when H^+ is exchanged by Na^+ . So it is very likely that due to the presence of a hydrophobic layer, ion such as Na^+ is not easily accessible to the resin surface unless a considerable amount of the initially adsorbed $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_2^{2+}$ ions get desorbed and replaced by hydrophilic ions. As result, the amount of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_2^{2+}$ desorption is very small at lower concentrations of the desorbing ions. Lindenbaum and Boyd⁴ obtained an increase in entropy in the exchange of Li^+ for Cs^+ in crosslinked polymethacrylate exchangers and this preference for Li^+ has been explained by assuming a specific association, i.e. site binding between Li^+ and the carboxylate group of the exchanger, with the release of water molecules. Further, dilatometric measurements¹⁴ with linear polymethacrylate have shown that a volume increase of ca 3 ml per equivalent occurs

in the system when tetramethylammonium counter ions are replaced by Li^+ or Na^+ . If water is released in site binding, an appreciable positive contribution to ΔS° also would be expected¹⁵. These effects have been ascribed to a competition between water of hydration and anion for a position near a given cation and ultimately to the charge distributions, polarizabilities, and effective field strengths of the participating ions¹⁶. Similar assumptions may be made here to explain the cation sequence in the exchange of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_2^{2+}$ by the monovalent ions in the present work.

To investigate the role of ionic hydration in the exchange reactions¹⁷, the desorption experiments have also been done in 50% ethanol-water medium (Fig. 1) at different concentrations of Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Rb^+ and Cs^+ . It can be noted that with each of the desorbing electrolytes the release of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_2^{2+}$ from the resin matrix is much higher than in the pure aqueous medium. The order of preference for the resin is $\text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Li}^+ > \text{Rb}^+ > \text{Cs}^+$, which is different as observed in pure aqueous solution. This behaviour may be attributed to the altered solvation of these ions, the resulting ionic sizes, their activities and the dielectric constant effects on coulombic interactions.

The selectivity coefficients of the exchanging ions in aqueous medium have been computed as in our previous paper¹¹ from the following relation,

$$K_{\text{Co}(\text{tn})_2^{2+}}^{\text{Li}^+} = \frac{[\bar{i}^{\text{Li}^+}]^{1/2} [\text{Co}(\text{tn})_2^{2+}]^{1/2}}{[\text{Co}(\text{tn})_2^{2+}]^{1/2} [i^{\text{Li}^+}]^{1/2}}$$

where the bracket and the bar mean the concentrations of the ions in the solution and resin phases respectively. The distribution coefficients have

Fig. 2. Plots showing correlation of selectivity coefficient against hydrated ionic radius and the reciprocal of the Debye Hückel parameter, a° , in aqueous medium.

been calculated from the equation $\lambda_i = \frac{\bar{m}_i}{m_i}$, where $\bar{m}_i$ and m_i are the concentrations of the species i in the solid and aqueous phases. According to these values (Table I) the exchanging ability of the ions

TABLE I—EXCHANGE PROPERTIES OF $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_2^+$ FROM $\text{Na-Co}(\text{tn})_2$ -IRC-50 AGAINST VARIOUS MONOVALENT IONS IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM

Electrolyte used	Concentration of the electrolyte (M)	Distribution coefficient	Selectivity coefficient
LiCl	0.25	4.13	0.472
	0.40	3.86	0.520
	0.50	3.88	0.588
NaCl	0.25	2.66	0.289
	0.40	3.02	0.369
	0.50	3.27	0.453
KCl	0.25	2.05	0.179
	0.40	2.18	0.236
	0.50	2.47	0.305
RbCl	0.25	1.80	0.153
	0.40	1.96	0.202
	0.50	2.11	0.245
CsCl	0.25	1.68	0.134
	0.40	1.80	0.179
	0.50	2.05	0.235
NH_4Cl	0.25	5.85	0.772
	0.30	5.89	0.847
	0.40	6.10	1.010

in pure aqueous medium may be placed in the sequence: $\text{NH}_4^+ > \text{Li}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Rb}^+ > \text{Cs}^+$. The greater desorbing power of NH_4^+ is possibly due to the low pH of NH_4Cl solution in the concentration

range studied where the high exchangeability of H^+ comes into play.

In an attempt to correlate the relative affinities of the desorbing ions for the resin matrix with their sizes, plots of $\log(\text{selectivity coefficient})$ against hydrated ionic radius¹⁸ and the reciprocal of the Debye Hückel parameter¹⁹, a° , i.e. the distance of closest approach between the counter ion and the fixed ionic group, have been made (Fig. 2). The latter plot is, however, on the basis of the simple electrostatic model of Pauley¹⁰ which assumes that coulombic interaction between the counter ions and the fixed ionic groups is the predominant factor and the counter ions in the ion exchanger are found at their distance of closest approach to the fixed ionic groups. It is interesting to note that both the parameters give linear relation suggesting that both hydrated ionic radius as well as $\frac{1}{a^\circ}$ may be used for correlating the relative selectivities of the monovalent ions for the resin.

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